

Users	Tweets (N)	Participation	Marijuana use			Marijuana legalisation arguments			
			Industrial	Medicinal	Recreational	Pro-legalisation	Anti-legalisation	Balanced	No argument
Total	88								
National	32	17/04/2015	0	12	20	19	3	3	7
Financial Review	5	17/04/2015		2	3	3	1		1
ABC News	4	29/10/2016		2	2	3		1	
QandA	1	13/11/2019			1			1	
News.com.au	1	8/10/2019			1			1	
The Australian	1	27/09/2019			1		1		
Nine News Australia	2	26/09/2019		1	1	1			1
SBS Australia	1	6/04/2017		1		1			
7NEWS Australia	1	2/01/2017			1	1			
crickey_news	1	2/11/2016			1		1		
SBS News	2	13/04/2016		2		1			
10 News First	1	10/02/2016		1					1
The Feed SBS	2	11/08/2015		2		2			
The Saturday Paper	1	15/11/2019			1	1			
A.P.S.A.D	3	17/10/2019			3	2			2
TGA	1	21/08/2019		1					1
Legalise Now	5	24/10/2018			5	4			1
ACT	7		0	1	6	4	0	0	3
ABC Canberra	2	20/02/2019			2				2
Canberra Times	5	27/03/2015		1	4	4			1
NSW	12		0	5	7	3	0	2	7
10 News First Sydney	1	10/02/2016		1					1
7NEWS Sydney	3	25/07/2018		1	2	1		2	
Nine News Sydney	5	23/07/2014		2	3	1			4
The Daily Telegraph	3	1/09/2016		1	2	1			2
QLD	13		0	6	7	6	0	2	5
10 News First Queensland	2	10/05/2016		2					2
7NEWS Brisbane	4	21/06/2018		1	3	2		2	
Brisbane Times	2	28/09/2019		1	1	2			
Nine News Gold Coast	1	26/09/2019			1				1
Nine News Queensland	3	15/10/2017		2	1	2			1
The Courier-Mail	1	27/12/2019			1				1
SA	13		1	8	4	8	0	1	3
10 News First Adelaide	3	10/02/2016		3		2			1
7NEWS Adelaide	2	22/07/2014		1	1	1		1	
ABC Adelaide	3	18/10/2018	1		2	1			1
Nine News Adelaide	2	1/02/2018		2		1			1
The Advertiser & Sunday Mail	3	19/02/2017		2	1	3			
VIC	5		0	4	1	4	0	0	1
7NEWS Melbourne	1	3/09/2015		1		1			
Nine News Melbourne	2	1/03/2017		1	1	1			1
The Age	2	7/11/2016		2		2			
WA	6		0	2	4	3	0	1	2
10 News First Perth	1	10/02/2016		1					1
7NEWS Perth	1	26/09/2019			1				1
Nine News Perth	2	29/06/2018			2	1		1	
Perth Now / Sunday Times	2	5/10/2014		1	1	2			

5%
0%

Users (Adult Dope Debate)	Rec Tweets (N)	Participation	Marijuana legalisation arguments			
			Pro-legalisation	Anti-legalisation	Balanced	No argument
Total (including Legalise Now N=29)	51	121%	47%	8%	18%	31%
Australian news media outlets (N=26)	42	100%	57%	10%	21%	38%
National media representation (N=8)	11	26%	64%	36%	27%	27%
State media representation (N=24)	31	74%	39%	0%	19%	42%
ACT news media outlets (N=2)	6	19%	50%	0%	0%	50%
NT news media outlets (N=0)	0	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
NSW news media outlets (N=3)	7	23%	14%	0%	29%	57%
QLD news media outlets (N=5)	7	23%	29%	0%	29%	43%
SA news media outlets (N=4)	6	19%	67%	0%	17%	17%
TAS news media outlets (N=0)	0	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
VIC news media outlets (N=1)	1	3%	0%	0%	0%	100%
WA news media outlets (N=3)	4	13%	50%	0%	25%	25%
Users			Marijuana legalisation arguments			
			Pro-legalisation	Anti-legalisation	Balanced	No argument
Total (rec only)	47		24	4	9	16
National	21	17/02/2016	12	4	3	3
Financial Review	3	17/02/2016	2	1		
ABC News	2	22/10/2019	1		1	
QandA	1	13/11/2019			1	
News.com.au	1	8/10/2019			1	
The Australian	1	27/09/2019		1		
Nine News Australia	1	26/09/2019				1
7NEWS Australia	1	2/01/2017	1			
crickey_news	1	2/11/2016		1		
The Saturday Paper	1	15/11/2019	1			1
A.P.S.A.D	3	17/10/2019	2			1
TGA	1	21/08/2019		1		
Legalise Now	5	24/10/2018	5			
ACT	6	27/03/2015	3	0	0	3
ABC Canberra	2	20/02/2019				2
Canberra Times	4	27/03/2015	3			1
NSW	7	17/04/2018	1	0	2	4
7NEWS Sydney	2	25/09/2019			2	
Nine News Sydney	3	26/09/2019				3
The Daily Telegraph	2	17/04/2018	1			1
QLD	7	21/06/2018	2	0	2	3
7NEWS Brisbane	3	21/06/2018	1		2	
Brisbane Times	1	28/09/2019	1			
Nine News Gold Coast	1	26/09/2019				1
Nine News Queensland	1	26/09/2019				1
The Courier-Mail	1	27/12/2019				1
SA	6	1/02/2018	4	0	1	1
7NEWS Adelaide	1	25/09/2019			1	
ABC Adelaide	2	18/10/2018	2			
Nine News Adelaide	2	1/02/2018	1			1
The Advertiser & Sunday Mail	1	28/01/2020	1			
VIC	1	26/09/2019	0	0	0	1
Nine News Melbourne	1	26/09/2019				1
WA	4	29/06/2018	2	0	1	1
7NEWS Perth	1	26/09/2019				1
Nine News Perth	2	29/06/2018	1		1	
Perth Now / Sunday Times (Seven West Media W	1	31/01/2020	1			

UID	User	Handle	Date	Tweet	Stance	Evidence based Research	Compares cannabis control to alcohol and tobacco laws	Comments	Retweets	Likes	Hashtags
1	WATCH2o	@watch2o	#####	It should be adults human right to be able to choose to use cannabis in our private lives.	Pro-legalisation			0	1	14	1
2	Sister Bernadette E. O'Malley	@SisterOMalley	#####	Stop wasting taxpayers money & punishing people for it. It can cause greater harm than the plant. #Auspol				1	0	1	4
3	Ben Wilson	@wilsonb3	#####	And alcohol can potentially turn you into a vicious murderer. The lock out laws were not in response to cannabis smokers...				0	0	9	0
4	bort	@gnarnigiana	#####	"One Australian city." You mean Canberra, the national capital?				0	0	10	0
5	bonfire	@bonfireblaze	#####	Irrelevant, people will use it anyway. Might as well tax and regulate it to minimise harm and criminal activity.				0	0	4	0
6	Daren Connor Flag of Australia	@connor_daren	#####	Critics say 'don't eat eggs'. Critics say 'Batman Vs Superman was a good film'. Critics get it wrong the time. I've been advised by pain specialists, psychologists and GPs to use it. Let adults decide for themselves				0	0	4	0
7	Droplet	@connor_daren	#####	Just saying... [Embedded image] "We've seen a 20 fold increase in the amount of people using cannabis. And everyone is terrified that cannabis causes schizophrenia. In the UK there's actually, if anything, a declining incidence of schizophrenia, a declining incidence of psychosis. NOWHERE IN THE WORLD HAS CANNABIS BEEN RELATED TO AN INCREASE OF SCHIZOPHRENIA." Professor David Nutt DM, FRCP, FRCPsych, FMedSci. Chair of Independent Scientific Committee on Drugs (ISCD), President of the European College of Neuropsychopharmacology (ENCP), President-elect of the British Neuroscience Association, UK Director of the European Certificate and Masters in Affective Disorders Courses				0	0	4	0
8	Felipecoño. Shañan. Et-Yehudi	@felipcon	#####	Why don't you talk about the people dying with tobacco. \$40 in Australia... \$350 in Indonesia... for a pack of smokes... government make money on cigarettes and it kills a lot of people				0	0	3	0
9	Perth Pitches Inside 50!	@GunnRumer420	#####	Critics gonna critic				0	0	3	0
10	Angela Russo	@AussieGrobie	#####	Ab, Canberra. The capital of cannabis, fireworks and porn.				0	0	3	0
11	Sam Trey	@lujpe24	#####	Just like everyday drinking is bad for you so too is everyday weed. I used to be a bong rat and loved it but it made me lazy and my short term memory was rooted. It comes back when you stop though. Moderation is key.				0	0	2	0
12	Heidi Helen Pilypas	@heidi_helen	#####	People need to do their research and if they are living with an existing condition like schizophrenia, they should talk with a professional if they're at risk. It's not clear if cannabis can cause a psychotic disorder or only heighten an existing one.				1	0	3	0
13	ddong	@linyang95_ddong	#####	I'm glad the article did say the connection between marijuana and schizo is unclear with further research needed. I was quite impressed with the article, it was very fair on the positives and negatives.				2	0	2	0
14	LetsTalkAustralia	@Australalats	#####	The fact baby boomers still think it's a terrible drug is the reason we need to put them all on cruises.				3	0	2	0
15	The Cannulator™ Save Channel 31 & Stay Home	@Cannulator	#####	It is not a benign drug. Not everyone is a doomsdayer about it, but treating it like it cause no harm is naive. Like any drug legal or otherwise it requires at least modicum of responsible use.				0	0	1	0
16	Giram@Giram	@GiramGiram2	#####	So does alcohol				1	0	0	0
17	youcouldkillmeifuyouredforahundredyears	@Bomdignifrech3	#####	So can birth				0	0	1	0
18	Anna	@FuryinMe	#####	So does veganism				0	0	1	0
19	André H Flag of Australia	@EaseMehUpPz	#####	Eyes (preparing to get sledged)				0	0	0	0
20	ravinesh prasad	@PrasadRavinesh	#####	You can literally die of alcohol withdrawal but that's cool, apparently. Face with raised eyebrow				0	0	0	0
21	rustyvaag	@rustyvaag3	#####	Ah yes, of course... The anti drug brigade duly shuffle out the reeler madness rubbish...				1	0	0	0
22	Ryan	@Ryan_Aus06	#####	Of course not let talk about Alcohol & cigs which KILL People!				0	0	0	0
23	Grumbles	@Grumbly_Me	#####	Clearly the issues are it takes away profits from the tobacco companies				0	0	0	0
24	Michael	@Michael0184139	#####	I heard a see people die prematurely due to cigarettes ...never have I heard people divine or overdosing on cannabis...				0	0	0	0
25	Wahyne	@Wahyne66	#####	You have got to love Canberra, known for years for fireworks and porn - fireworks have gone so we will add weed. To top off circuses are banned. Bit of a confusing message for the kids in Canberra I reckon				0	0	0	0
26	ravinesh prasad	@PrasadRavinesh	#####	Tax payers money will be well used than. For taking care of people who will lose their job and over dose themselves on a regular basis and form a habit of it because it's legal now to use it.				0	0	0	0
27	Danushka	@dank125	#####	Clipping hands sign Clipping hands sign				1	0	0	0
28	Wait a minute	@Waitami615151	#####	sounds like http://news.com.au one of the "critics"?				0	0	0	0
29	Al Firenze	@Al_Firenze	#####	Have another puff				0	0	0	0
30	happymays	@happymays	#####	roll a J and chill the f out everyone				0	0	1	0
31	Will Budic	@will_bud	#####	I'm not sure. Didn't see said headlines about a VB truck crashing today? So VB is good, but not is bad?				0	0	1	0
32	Jack	@gmtaj	#####	Not for everyone, sure!				0	0	0	0
33	russeil camel watie	@l3camel	#####	Just like alcohol				0	0	0	0
34	russeil camel watie	@l3camel	#####	Genesis 1:11 And God said, Let the earth bring forth grass, the herb yielding seed, and the fruit tree yielding fruit after his kind, whose seed is in itself, upon the earth: and it was so				1	0	0	0
35	Pat Hall	@PatsPat	#####	Genesis 1:12 And the earth brought forth grass, and herb yielding seed after his kind, and the tree yielding fruit, whose seed was in itself, after his kind: and God saw that it was good.				0	0	0	0
36	SneakyTheArab	@Sneaky_Arab	#####	We need more correct information, the difference between cannabis oil which has the "hypnotic" component taken out of it and the smoking of joints. Cannabis oil which can be taken in food seems to help sick people and should be issued by prescription.				0	0	0	0
37	Philip Cocker	@philipcocker	#####	and it needs to be legalised here in QLD. I need it as it helps keep me seizure free and function like a normal person, without it I would be having 6 Grand mal seizures a week on a good day and be bed ridden for days at a time				0	0	0	0
38	Mark Andrew Lamb	@Markymark2173	#####	It does in some.				0	0	0	0
39	Monkey Flag of Australia	@HolmiDamon	#####	What about drinking alcohol? Face with tears of joy				0	0	0	0
40	PaddyOReilly	@PaddyOReilly	#####	Still frame from the Godfather				0	0	0	0
41	Earth globe americas	@ManfromMosmu	#####	Duh!				0	0	0	0
42	Boomer Corbett	@28DegreesSouth	#####	Rubbish!				0	0	0	0
43	28° South	@OIMate5	#####	Makes it want pizza				0	0	0	0
44	OI Mate	@vkrsek	#####	Same as what nicotine does to your lungs. Does that info stop anyone? The gov sure loves the tax revenue its sales generate though.				0	0	0	0
45	Droplet	@Waitami615151	#####	Curare, snake venom, arsenic, all manner of poisons are natural				0	0	0	0
46	Wendy Krusk	@LachlanPorter1	#####	It's a great decision my the Australian government, can't wait until it's in Victoria				0	0	0	0
47	Wait a minute	@lctcmPaul	#####	CAN?, it does and it also leads on to stronger drugs then violence, robbery, rape, divorce, car accidents and even suicide in many cases - not a real smart legislation at all..				2	0	0	0
48	Sheepy Boy	@Rbridge11	#####	That's like saying preaching leads on to molesting children. But you're not saying that are you?				0	0	3	0
49	Paradise NOW Church	@BozGozoid	#####	Reversed hand with middle finger extended				0	0	0	0
50	PattinTids	@FreedomSquid	#####	Trawling through http://news.com rots your brain too				0	0	0	0
51	Confessions of an Opium Eater	@justantweet	#####	Is Cannabis still the most widely researched drug on the planet? #auspol "critics say" might be a fact but is what they say a fact? Stop putting up garbage and put up facts!				0	0	1	1
52	FreedomSquid	@kingkongdonkey	#####	Cigarettes WILL give you cancer.				1	0	0	0
53	Droplet	@Cannulator	#####	So will smoking anything that burns.				0	0	0	0
54	justantweet	@YeahBrohamski	#####	It can lead to excessive consumption of Doritos.				1	0	1	0
55	kingkongdonkey	@YeahBrohamski	#####	It can lead to excessive consumption of Doritos.				1	0	1	0
56	The Cannulator™ Save Channel 31 & Stay Home	@Cannulator	#####	So will smoking anything that burns.				0	0	0	0
57	Yeah Brah	@YeahBrohamski	#####	It can lead to excessive consumption of Doritos.				1	0	1	0
58	D	@techbayyking2	#####	Image of smiling man with the word 'Yes' near his mouth				0	0	1	0
59	Negative squared latin capital letter a	@techbayyking2	#####	Image of smiling man with the word 'Yes' near his mouth				0	0	1	0
60	Negative squared latin capital letter b	@techbayyking2	#####	Image of smiling man with the word 'Yes' near his mouth				0	0	1	0
61	EEBCHAD IV	@techbayyking2	#####	Image of smiling man with the word 'Yes' near his mouth				0	0	1	0
62	Andrew Wirski	@AndrewWirski	#####	There is no drug that doesn't cause problems for someone. We are not all the same but that's no reason to demonize or ban marijuana. Prohibition didn't work.				0	0	0	0
63	Droplet	@RomonaPerry13	#####	What about if they each harvest & replenish 2 plants every day. (ring Uber drop off 2 plants & pick up 2 harvested plants from yesterday				0	0	0	0
64	Romona Perry	@RomonaPerry13	#####	Rolling on the floor laughing!				0	0	0	0
65	Droplet	@RomonaPerry13	#####	What about California? Full of vagrants & increased crime since legalised.				0	0	0	0
66	Romona Perry	@RomonaPerry13	#####	To the critics. Why don't you set your sights on alcohol and cigarettes? Do something constructive for a change and no I don't use it or intend to use it. #marijuana #auspol #laws #australia				0	0	3	4
67	lan_blackley	@lan_blackley	#####	To the critics. Why don't you set your sights on alcohol and cigarettes? Do something constructive for a change and no I don't use it or intend to use it. #marijuana #auspol #laws #australia				0	0	3	4
68	Headphone	@lan_blackley	#####	To the critics. Why don't you set your sights on alcohol and cigarettes? Do something constructive for a change and no I don't use it or intend to use it. #marijuana #auspol #laws #australia				0	0	3	4
69	Flag of Australia	@RayWombold	#####	Major studies have confirmed that listening to experts can lead to psychotic disorders.				0	0	0	0
70	Ray	@RayWombold	#####	Exploding head				0	0	0	0

Analysis & Policy Observatory (APO)	@apogau	AU	https://twitter.com/apogau is embedded in Twitter icon on https://www.fox.com.au/ Legacy content appears in Google search results for "Analysis & Policy Observatory twitter", https://twitter.com/apogau/status/1180221374497247 page does not exist and @APOtagau members in posts appear with no link because the profile does not exist? Also mentions Swinburne APO?
"Yonnie"			
Derek Connor	@dconnor_au	AU	
Flag of Australia			
United Nations		INT	
Centre for Disease Control		INT	
MaggieHood		INT	
FifeHood		INT	
Dr Fiona Chalmers (Executive)		INT	
Laura James (SA SA CEO)		INT	
Alan Benjamin (NSW Registrar)		INT	
Steve Deacon (SA Business Leader)		INT	
Luke Foley (NSW Opposition Leader)		NSW	
Mick Barr		NSW	
Melissa Fie (Health Consumers Queensland)		QLD	
WV News Tasmania	@WVNews	TAS	
Nightly News 7 Tasmania	@7NewsTAS	TAS	
WV News (22 not including NT)	@WVNews	WA/NT/SA	
WA Today	@WAtoday	WA	
William West (SA Alcohol Unit)		WA	
Clare Haskewell (The Office of Drug Policy Action WP 2003)		INT	
Research Fellow & Executive Director of Drug Policy Research		INT	
Clare Haskewell, OBA's managing director of development		INT	
Capital Cities Centre (CCI) Demolishes the War on Drugs - Co-founder of UAP		INT	https://www.capitalcitiescentre.com.au/news/2016/04/06/
Sophia Moorhead		INT	
Legislative Councils (WA)			
Australian Inland Ferry			
Chief Medical Officers			
Ministerial Drug and Alcohol Forum (MDAF)			
man			
BBC			
RoadFeed			
The New Daily			
Inspire (NSW)			
Justice (NSW)			
ACT Police			
NSW Police			
NT Police			
LA Police			
TAS Police			
VIC Police			
WA POL			
State Police Chief/Commissioner/Alcohol General			
Health Consumers Council			
Brian Walters (Drug Free Australia)			
Canada Life			
Jimmy Mackinn			
Carrollville Club Australia			
AAA Foundation for Traffic Safety			
Prof David Nutt			
Independent Scientific Committee on Drugs (ISCD)			
European College of Neuro-psychiatry members (ECNP)			
British Neuroscience Association			
European Certificate and Masters in Addictive Disorders Courses			
CSIRO	@CSIRO		
Drugs&AlcoholReview	@BMSAD_DAR		
The Lancet			
The Lancet Psychiatry			
The Lancet Public Health			
Nature			
Prof Wayne Hall			
Prof Michael Lymbay			
Dr Sharon Hunter			
Dr Sharon Davis			
Prof Nicholas Loxton			
Prof Michael Foley			
Nella Schell			
Prof Murray Viner			
Leahy			
Medfield			
Stephen Kraussner (Medfield Group)			
Adam Jackson (Medfield Group)			
Ted O'Brien (Member for Fairfax)			
Anthony Perry (SA Lawyer)			
Bill Fong (Lawyer criminal lawyer)			
Matthew Pallett (The Pallant)			
The Doctors Union			
Jason Jordan			
Medical Cannabis Research Australia			
Debra Leigh Lynch (Medical Cannabis Users Association)			
Ben Oakley			
Laura Bryant (Pharm)			
Steven Day (Pharm)			
Ally Tregear (Pharm)			
Genève Tregear (Pharm)			
Lily Frazier (Pharm)			
Michael Public			
JD			
Alan Carpenter			
National Free Club			
Scott Morrison			
Malcolm Turnbull			
Geoffrey Blainey			
Christian Porter			
Jeremy Hanson (ACT Shadow Attorney General)			
Daniel Andrews			
Geoff Birt			
JP Morrison			
Susan Ley			
Carrenson Dick (Health Minister)			
Steve Dizon (Shadow MP)			
Rebecca Brindley			
Shane Rattenbury	@PeterDutton_MP		
Peta Crellin	@NACMcCasimMP		
Nicholas Hironaka			
Grantfield MC			
Selwyn			
Dr Debra Heath (VIC Medical Centre)			
Prof Mark Rosen (VIC)			
Journal of Nature (VIC)			
Jeff Deane (SA researcher)			
ANACAD members are experts with experience relating to drugs and alcohol.			
Min Kay Hui	Chair		
Professor Steve Abbot	Deputy Chair		
Associate Professor Robert Ali	Member		
Ms John Rigney	Member		
Associate Professor Diana Egerton-Warburton	Member		
Ms Jo Baker	Member		
Mr Frank Quinlan	Member		
Deputy Superintendent Anthony Fleming	Member		
Dr James Fitzpatrick	Member		
Associate Professor James Ward	Member		
Ms Rebecca Ling	Member		
Dr Nicola Lee	Member		
Mr Jack Hogg	Member		
Adjunct Associate Professor Peta Hultman	Observer		
ADVISORY COMMITTEE MEMBERS			
Robert Ali	Australian National Advisory Council on Alcohol and Drugs		
Jo Baker	Australian National Advisory Council on Alcohol and Drugs		
Janet Brown	New South Wales Poison Information Centre		
Louise Doughtart	National Drug and Alcohol Research Centre		
Adrian Dunlop	Hunter New England Local Health District Drug and Alcohol Clinical Services		
Diana Egerton-Warburton	Australian National Advisory Council on Alcohol and Drugs		
Nedra David	St Vincent's Hospital Drug and Alcohol Service		
Michael Ford	National Drug and Alcohol Research Centre		
Tony Fleming	Australian National Advisory Council on Alcohol and Drugs		
Brenda Lloyd	Turning Point		
Jochem Mulder	National Research Centre for Environmental Toxicology		
Christine Nease	National Drug and Alcohol Research Centre		
Shane Nelson	Australian Institute of Criminology		
Ang Penick	National Drug and Alcohol Research Centre		
Alison Piller	National Drug and Alcohol Research Centre		
Amanda Reddyburgh	National Drug and Alcohol Research Centre		
Darlene Scott	Turning Point		
Rachel Stubbart	National Drug and Alcohol Research Centre		